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Rearrangement of 2'-Hydroxychalcone derivatives and their biological activity

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2'-Hydroxychalcones, being the initial compounds in the synthesis of various types of flavonoids [1-3], are also used as irreplaceable key products for the preparation of various heterocyclic systems with wide range of biological activity.

For this purpose, a number of nitrogen-containing derivatives of heterocyclic systems **4-8** were synthesized starting from chalcones **1-3**, obtained by an efficient modified method as a result of the condensation of a suitable 2'-hydroxyacetophenone with the corresponding aldehydes in the presence of DMF and powdered caustic potassium (yield up to 89%) [4]. Boiling substituted chalcones **1-3** in an alcoholic solution with phenyl hydrazine gives the corresponding phenyl pyrazolines **4-6** in a short time.

In the PMR spectra (in DMSO) of phenyl pyrazolines **4-6**, the signals of the 4-CH₂ and 5-H protons of the pyrazoline ring form the ABX system: 3.9-4.0 ppm. (d.d, 1H, -H_A); 3.2-3.8 ppm (d.d, 1H, -H_B); 5.3-5.5 ppm (d.d, 1H, -H_X); J_{AB}=17.6-18.0 Hz, J_{AX}=6.6-6.96 Hz, J_{BX}=12.1-12.8 Hz.

As an example of a reaction in which a carbonyl group is involved, the reaction (thiolation reaction) of substituted chalcones **1-2** with thiopurine was studied.

Heating chalcones **1-2** with thiourea and sodium hydroxide in absolute ethanol gives 2-thioxopyrimidines **7, 8**. In the PMR spectra of 2-thioxopyrimidines **7, 8**, the signal of the 5-H aromatic proton shifts downfield under the influence of the sulfur atom by 0.4 ppm. compared to the original products.

Consequently, 2'-hydroxychalcones **1-3** under the influence of phenyl hydrazine and thiopurine are rearranged into heterocyclic systems, with different nature substitutes. Taking into account the studies of the biological activity of a number of synthesized derivatives of chalcones [4, 5] and nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds [6, 7], we continued the study of synthesized new derivatives of compound **4-8**. The group of obtained synthetic analogs of natural flavonoids was transferred to the *in vitro* study for antimycobacterial activity against *M. Tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv in BACTEC-12B and Erdman Tuberculosis Antimicrobial Acquisition and Coordinating Facility (TAACF), Southern Research Institute, USA in comparison with rifampicin as a standard (effective dose 6.25 µg/ml). As a result of the studies, it was found that compounds **6** (69%) and **8** (50%) exhibit anti-tuberculosis activity. Thus, in this group of substances, compound **6** showed the greatest activity, but in terms of the magnitude of the pharmacological effect in the studied dose, it does not exceed the drug "Rifampicin". Apparently, in this case, the substituents of the series compounds **4-8** in the manifestation of anti-tuberculosis activity do not affect.

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